

A COUPLED VISCOELASTICITY AND MULLINS EFFECT MODEL FOR SOFT MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

A recently reported synthesized double network hydrogel consists of a covalently-crosslinked polyacrylamide network whose chains are long and ionically-crosslinked alginate hydrogels whose chains are relatively short. Such hydrogels are highly stretchable and tough. When they are stretched, the ionic network inside the hydrogels ruptures and absorb a large amount of energy whereas the covalent network keeps intact. In this work, we develop a coupled viscoelastic and Mullins-effect model to characterize the deformation behavior of the tough gel. We modify one of the elastic components in Zener model to be a damageable spring. We synthesized the tough gel described in the literature (Sun et al., Nature 2012) and conducted uniaxial tensile tests and stress relaxation tests to verify our model. We also investigated the two effects on three other soft materials, polyacrylate elastomer, Nitrile-Butadiene Rubber, and polyurethane. We find that our presented model is so robust that it can characterize all the four materials, with modulus ranging from a few tens of kilopascal to megapascal. The theory and experiment for all tested materials agree very well.

1 KEY RESULTS

Fig. 1 Rheological model with Mullins effect: a damageable spring in series with a Kelvin unit

The total stretch is equal to the stretch of Spring A multiplied with the stretch of Spring B,

$$\lambda_i = \lambda_i^A \lambda_i^B, \quad (1)$$

where the subscript $i = 1, 2$. The stress of Spring A is equal to the stress of Spring B plus the stress of the dashpot,

$$\sigma_i = \sigma_i^A = \sigma_i^B + \sigma_i^{dashpot}. \quad (2)$$

Spring A is characterized as an incompressible material with Mullins effect. The free energy of Spring A can be expressed as

$$W^A(\lambda_1^A, \lambda_2^A, \eta) = \eta \tilde{W}^A(\lambda_1^A, \lambda_2^A) + \phi(\eta), \quad (3)$$

where η is the damage variable. The damage function and the damage variable can be expressed as

$$\phi(\eta) = \int_1^\eta \left[(m + \beta W_m^A) \operatorname{erf}^{-1}(r(1-\eta) - W_m^A) \right] d\eta, \quad (4)$$

$$\eta = 1 - \frac{1}{r} \operatorname{erf} \left[(W_m^A - \tilde{W}^A) / (m + \beta W_m^A) \right], \quad (5)$$

The rate of deformation in the dashpot is related to the deviatoric stresses as

$$\frac{d\xi_1}{\xi_1 dt} = \frac{\sigma_1^{dev}}{2\chi}, \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{d\xi_2}{\xi_2 dt} = \frac{\sigma_2^{dev}}{2\chi}, \quad (7)$$

where χ is a constant denoting the viscosity coefficient of the dashpot.

Fig. 2 Experimental results and theoretical predictions for stress relaxation tests of the tough gel under different loading rates (a), (c) stress–stretch curves and (b), (d) stress–time history

KEY REFERENCES

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